

Table 2. Effect on ShR of frequent spraying of fungicides. TRRI, Aduthurai, India.

Fungicide	Frequency of spraying (d)	Disease intensity ^a
Carbendazim 0.1%	3	0 a
	5	0.6 a
	10	4.6 b
	15	7.4 c
Captafol 0.125%	3	3.4 b
	5	3.4 b
	10	4.6 b
	15	6.2 c
Unsprayed check	–	6.6 c

^a Means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.

medium and individual grains were inserted by forceps into the leaf sheaths of CO 43, a susceptible cultivar.

Only the boot leaf sheath was susceptible to the disease; all other leaf sheaths showed no symptoms.

Different fungicides were sprayed at boot leaf emergence. A grain containing the fungus was inserted into the boot leaf sheath 24 h later. Disease development was assessed at intervals. When the entire leaf sheath was infected, thus preventing panicle emergence, the plant was graded 9; grades 7, 5, 3, and 1 showed decreasing disease intensity, with 0 as no infection. Fungicide captafol and carbendazim effectively controlled the disease up to 10 d after spraying. But at 15 d after treatment, none of the fungicides gave any protection (Table 1).

These results suggest that captafol and carbendazim are only fungistatic against the pathogen, not fungicidal. For effective protection, fungicides must be sprayed more often than once in 15 d.

In another experiment, the fungicides were sprayed and the fungus was inoculated 24 h later. Spraying was repeated once every 3 d 5 times, every 5 d 3 times, every 10 d 2 times, and every 15 d 2 times. Final disease intensity was assessed 3 d before harvest.

Carbendazim sprayed every 3 or 5 d gave complete protection throughout the crop period. Captafol sprays at intervals of 3, 5, or 10 d and carbendazim sprayed at 10-d intervals also gave significant protection. However, the fungicides sprayed at 15-d intervals were ineffective (Table 2). □

Chemical control of rice false smut

S. Ray, Nematology Department, Orissa University of Agriculture and Technology, (OUAT), Bhubaneswar 751003, India

False smut caused by *Ustilagoidea virens* (Cke) Tak. is a minor disease that usually occurs sporadically in ricefields. It rarely becomes serious in susceptible varieties.

We conducted a fungicidal trial in 1982 on CR1014, a popular susceptible

variety, with 10 treatments in a randomized block design with 3 replications. The chemicals were sprayed 4 times at 5-d intervals at the boot leaf stage. Disease incidence was calculated as percentage of panicles showing smutted grains in a randomly selected 1-m² area in each treatment.

CuO and TB significantly reduced disease incidence (see table). There was no significant difference in yield due to treatments. □

Effect of fungicidal sprays on false smut incidence. OUAT, Bhubaneswar, India, 1982. ^a

Treatment	Application rate (ai/liter)	Disease incidence angular (%) values	Grain yield (t/ha)
Copper oxychloride (CuO)	2.5 g	0.42 (0.16)	2.0
Thiophanate benzyl (TB)	0.2 ml	0.63 (0.03)	1.8
Captafol	1.2 g	4.41 (0.59)	1.9
Maneb	1.8 g	3.12 (0.32)	1.9
Benomyl	1.0 g	5.67 (1.00)	1.8
Carbendazim	0.5 g	4.13 (0.59)	1.9
Zineb	1.8 ml	1.66 (0.13)	2.1
MBC	0.5 g	4.45 (0.63)	1.9
Organophosphate	0.5 ml	6.37 (1.31)	2.1
Check (water)	–	4.41 (0.61)	2.0
CD (0.05)	–	2.18	ns

^a Mean of 3 replications.

Silica reduces disease on upland rice in a high rainfall area

M. Yamauchi and M. D. Winslow, International Institute of Tropical Agriculture (IITA), P.M.B. 5320, Oyo Road, Ibadan, Nigeria

The effect of silica in reducing disease in lowland rice is well known, but reports of its effect on upland rice are few. Highly weathered, leached acid soils in

high rainfall upland areas might be expected to be low in available silica.

Trials at IITA's high rainfall station at Onne in southeast Nigeria examined the effect of silica on diseases in upland rice. The soil is a Typic Paleudult with coarse-loamy texture, pH 4.3, and low effective cation exchange capacity (2.86 meq/ 100 g soil in the top 15 cm). Exchangeable Al is the dominant cation. Minerals in the clay fraction are mainly kaolinite, with a small amount of

Effect of silica application on fungal diseases of upland rice. ^a Onne, Nigeria, 1986 wet season.

Variety	Silica treatment	Disease score ^b			
		Sheath blight	Leaf scald	Neck blast	Grain discoloration
ITA212 (lowland semidwarf)	Without	1.7	3.7	3.0	7.0
	With	1.0	1.7	2.3	3.7
ITA303 (upland semidwarf)	Without	3.7	5.7	4.3	5.0
	With	3.0	4.3	2.3	3.0
OS6 (upland tall)	Without	1.0	1.0	4.3	3.0
	With	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0

^a Means of 3 replications. ^b Standard evaluation system for rice.

ITA212, a lowland variety, also yields well in the high rainfall uplands. But it is susceptible to grain discoloration (left). Silica greatly reduced the disease (right).

goethite. Annual rainfall averages 2,500 mm.

Silica as sodium silicate was applied before sowing at 400 kg/ha. Control and treated plots received 60-26-50 kg NPK/ha.

Disease intensity was markedly reduced on silica-treated plots (see table). The greatest effect was in reducing grain discoloration (see figure) and neck blast. Varieties differ in inherent resistance to these diseases; generally, semidwarfs are most susceptible. However, all varieties tested benefited from silica application. □

White leaf streak disease on rice in India

D.K. Nayak, H.S. Chakrabarti, and A. Pal, Rice Research Station (RRS), Chinsurah, Hooghly, West Bengal, India

White leaf streak disease was first reported by Deighton and Shaw in Papua New Guinea in 1960. The causal organism was designated as *Rumularia oryzae*. Subsequently, the fungus was renamed *Mycovellosiella oryzae* (Deighton & Shaw) Deighton. In India *Mycovellosiella* (= *Ramularia*) was recorded on several dicotyledonous plants. Until now there has been no report of the occurrence of this genus on cereals except for sorghum in India.

The disease was noticed in the ricefields of RRS Chinsurah, in Sep-Oct 1984. Pronounced symptoms appeared on cv. Ratna in Oct during the milk to soft dough stage. The disease was again

recorded in March 1985 but at lower severity.

Initial spots on the leaves are 0.5-2.5 mm long and 0.5-1.0 mm wide, oblong, white to creamish white, delimited by narrow brown margins,

Cellular inclusions in rice grassy stunt virus (GSV)-infected rice

F. C. Sta. Cruz and H. Hibino, IRRI

GSV-infected TN 1 plants were collected 1 mo after inoculation for electron microscope observation. Ultrathin sections showed an association of two types of inclusions in GSV-infected plants. No similar structures were observed in healthy plants.

Fibrils grouped in bundles were abundant in mesophyll and phloem cells. The fibrillar inclusions were free either in the nucleus or in the cytoplasm

1. Fibrillar inclusions (fi) in nucleus (n) and cytoplasm of a mesophyll cell (35,000X). m = mitochondria.

2. Tubular inclusions (ti) associated with tiny particles in a sieve tube of GSV-infected rice leaf (35,000X). m = mitochondria. cw = cell wall. st = sieve tube.

amphigenous, and interveinal. They spread basipetally from the leaf tips in a linear manner. The spots gradually coalesce and form white streaks on both surfaces of the leaves. □

(Fig. 1) or bounded with membrane in the cytoplasm. Similar inclusions were also found in vacuole and chloroplasts.

Another type of inclusion observed in the sieve tube consisted of tubular structures associated with particles 18 nm in diameter (Fig. 2). The occurrence of tubular structures was less frequent than that of fibrillar inclusions.

Similar fibrillar inclusions were observed in plants infected with maize stripe virus, rice stripe virus, and rice hoja blanca virus. Those viruses are similar to GSV in morphology and vector-virus interactions. The four can be classified in the same group. □

Effect of neem oil on tungro (RTV) infection in susceptible and resistant varieties

K.E.A. Aiyathan and P. Narayanasamy, Plant Pathology Department, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Coimbatore 641003, India

RTV-susceptible and resistant cultivars were inoculated using 1, 3, and 5 viruliferous green leafhoppers (GLH) *Nephotettix virescens* per plant. Neem

Effect of neem oil on RTV infection in susceptible and resistant varieties inoculated using different numbers of insects. Coimbatore, India.